

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF A MOTHER IN THE NOVELS OF "AS I LAY DYING" BY WILLIAM FAULKNER AND "DUNYONING ISHLARI" BY O'TKIR HOSHIMOV

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Abstract: This thesis delves deeply into the analysis of the lives, works, and writing styles of two authors—O'tkir Hoshimov from Eastern literature and William Faulkner from Western literature—who have nearly identical ideals, purposes, and storytelling techniques. This comparative study examines how William Faulkner and O'tkir Hoshimov depict human suffering and moral strength in their literary works.

Annotatsiya: Bu tezis bir-biriga qariyb o'xshash bo'lgan g'oyalar, maqsadlar va hikoya yozish usullariga ega Sharq adabiyotidan O'tkir Hoshimov va G'arb adabiyotidan Uilyam Foulkner kabi ikki yozuvchining yozish usullari, asarlari va hayotining tahliliga chuqur e'tibor qaratadi. Bu qiyosiy tadqiqot Uilyam Foulkner va O'tkir Hoshimov inson azoblari va axloqiy kuchini o'z adabiy asarlarida qanday tasvirlaganliklarini o'rganadi.

Аннотация: Данная работа представляет собой всесторонний сравнительный анализ жизни, литературного наследия и стилевых особенностей двух выдающихся писателей — представителя восточной литературы Ўткира Хошимова и представителя западной литературы Уильяма Фолкнера. Несмотря на различие их культурных и географических контекстов, оба автора обладают поразительно схожими идеалами, нравственными взглядами и повествовательными приёмами. Исследование направлено на выявление того, как Фолкнер и Хошимов изображают сложность человеческих страданий, стойкость и нравственную силу своих героев, подчёркивая универсальность человеческого опыта в разных литературных традициях.

Keywords: William Fulkner, O'tkir hoshimov, motherhood, family, humanism, moral principles, As I lay dying, Dunyoning ishlari, characters, sacrifice.

Introduction.

This comparative study of two authors with diverse setting and with almost the similar themes like moral principles, familial bonds, social values allows us to explore the shared human experiences felt across the different cultures. Despite cultural and geographical differences, they can serve as excellent examples of writers with similar literary techniques who attempt different approaches to reveal shared realities about humanitarian society. Additionally, the mother is emphasized as the primary emblem of human yearning, selflessness, and moral fortitude in the novels "Dunyoning ishlari" and "As I lay dying." One of them is William Faulkner was born in the late nineteenth century and mostly well-known for his complex narrative style with his best works like As I lay dying The sound and the fury as a modern author and who win the noble prize in the twentieth century in American society. In spite of the fact that he was born after American civil war it was reflected on his novels and made the topics of slavery, colonisation the basic themes for him. One of his best literary works is As I Lay Dying and it introduces the story of the Bundren family's travel to Jefferson city to hold burial ceremony of their mother, Addie, revealing each member's inner struggle and conflicting thoughts and learns human resilience. O'tkir Hoshimov stands as one of the leading uzbek writers of narration whose main attention on most of his literary works were on the themes of family

love, humanity and moral insight into human nature. His works primarily focus on moral principles, relationships among family members, and the struggles of ordinary humans during times of social and political instability. *Dunyoning ishlari* as a brilliant work of O'tkir Hoshimov discovers the life of simple Uzbek people living in countryside, capturing their spiritual strength and putting emphasis particularly on the interconnection between a mother and her son.

Main body

The object of this research paper is dedicated to the analysis and the comparison of main characters of two novels exactly the mother's role with different conditions in the variety of societies. One of the other Authors who raised a voice of this topic Jill Bergman (1996) thinks that mother has two distinct roles in William Faulkner's novel: one is destroying ideology of mother, another is supporting idea of a mother and for him it would be unfair or diminishing to select one.

Narrative presence of mother.

With narrative point mother Addie does not appear chapters with her own voice as she is dead from the very beginning of a novel and it is kind of that she rules with the absence of talk and known through other characters' inner thoughts. The family members long- distance trip for the funeral of their mother is not merely physical but symbolic of their fight with sense, sin, and interest-themselves. Each difficulty which Bundren's family undergo during their journey symbolizes different meanings and it seems that even after dying mother Addie plays a significant role to make family's association stronger. Her death becomes an occasion that reveals self-esteem, competing narratives, and the failure of meaningful communicating among them. Even being not alive, Addie's body becomes a narrative factor —Her children's motivations are driven by her memory, while the story is physically propelled forward by her decaying corpse. Her presence demonstrates that a mother's significance transcends death by obfuscating the distinction between life and death. She simultaneously unites and divides her family, becoming a symbol of corruption and connection. However, in *Dunyoning Ishlari*, the mother's moral presence lessens tensions and promotes harmony. While the mother's disappearance is lamented in *Dunyoning Ishlari*, Addie's passing takes the entire family—aside from the young character—on a trip without much sadness or depression. While mother Addie is absent at the start of the book *As I Lay Dying*, the mother in *Dunyoning Ishlari* is the main character and is represented throughout novel with different stories of people centralized on the topic of mother. Mother can speak can direct, can alleviate problems.

Symbolic function --- what the mother represents.

Everything has a metaphorical meaning in the novel of *As I lay dying*. The mother of the main character stands in for the symbols of coming together to overcome the challenges that Bundren's family encounters on route to the city of Jefferson. Unbreakable connection between life and death. Her passing away is a catalyst that makes her family to confront their internal difficulties and moral failings rather than an end. Through the role of Addie Faulkner attempts to familiarize readers with the identities of mothers in the South of America during that era through Addie. Faulkner demonstrates how a mother's identity is frequently sacrificed to meet the needs of others, making her a representation of both creation and loss. In contrast, the presence of mother is symbolized as a means of purity, goodness and endless love despite any situation which makes other characters love the role of mother in *Dunyoning ishlari* by O'tkir Hoshimov. Unlike the family members of Addie, here the mother herself is a symbol of fighting against problems in daily life sacrificing herself for her children's blessing and future. This is one aspect of Uzbek nationality, that period's traditions and conditions. At that time honesty, humanity, humility and respect, hope for the future were the main

themes of novels and it is shown in O'tkir Hoshimov's book through the characters who are associated with the role and importance of mother, her advice and guidance.

Conclusion.

Comparing the commonalities and differences of these two novels I understand that the reasons why they stand as the best works of their authors are the moral principles they integrate and the role of the mother as the main personage to make other characters or individuals to stand face to face with questions of responsibility, sensibility and identity in various situations. Making comparisons and contrasts help readers to shape the idea of motherhood in diverse settings with diverse conditions. In these two works, both writers tried to enrich our understanding of how maternal figures can be employed to question or sustain orders in the society.

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